

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

Agbor, Emmanuel A.¹, Obongha, Ukpali E.², Ita, Emmanuel. E.³

^{1,2,3}Department of Urban and Regional Planning Cross River University of Technology, Calabar

ABSTRACT: The Ancient city of ‘CALABAR’ often interpreted as “Come And Live And Be At Rest” has experienced insecurity and safety for over a decade due to rapid population growth and urbanization. The urban settings have also influenced criminal activities and disorder especially the physical form of the metropolis and its diverse economic activities. The increase crime rate is also attributed to the city’s social activity pattern and the structure of its transportation network which distributes traffic to all the neighborhoods within and around Calabar Metropolis. The aim of this study is to appraise the insecurity situation in the ancient city of Calabar and the consequences on the residents in the metropolis. The specific objectives are; to identify the major types of criminal activities in Calabar metropolis; to determine the cause of such criminal activities in the study area; and to examine the physical form and structure of the area under study. The Pearson’s Product Moment statistical techniques was employed to test the relationship between population and crime. At 4.345 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the P-value was less than the chosen alpha of .05, the null Hypothesis was therefore rejected confirming a significant relationship between population and crime in the study area. The study further revealed increase criminal activities in the inner-city neighborhoods and the Gated and rich neighborhoods in the study area due to the deteriorating quality of urban life and poor urban planning and design.

KEYWORDS: Crime, Felonies, Misdemeanors, Population, Safety, Security.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world is experiencing the second phase of urbanization phenomenon since the industrial revolution in the mid-19th century. The current rate of urbanization and urban growth is unprecedented. The United Nations survey in 1800, revealed that only 2.00 percent of the world population was urbanized. By 1850, not only more than 5.0 percent of the global population was urbanized and no society had more than half of its population living in cities except London which had more than one million people. The percentage of world’s population living in urban centres increased between 1800 and 1985 from 14.00 percent to 43.00 percent as indicated below on table 1. Currently in year 2020 the world urban population has increased to 2.9 billion as reported by the United Nations and Population Reference Bureau (1982).

Currently, most African nations are experiencing the fastest rate of urbanization in the world without a corresponding increase in the essential basic infrastructure which is creating serious economic, social, political and environmental related problems. Between 1970-1995 the average African country’s urban population grew by 5.2 percent per annum while its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) declined by 0.66 percent per annum Hicks (1998). Urban population growth has been on the increase in Nigeria since the pre-colonial era. Okeke (1998) asserts that Nigeria urban centres are amongst the fastest growing cities in the world. For instance, in 1921 Nigeria had a total of 29 urban centres. By 1931, the number drop to 27 as a result of the political boundary delineations between the Federal Republic of Nigeria and the British Cameroun protectorate. The number of urban centres reached 56 in 1953 and between 1963 and 1991 the number of urban centres rose to 182 and 359 respectively. There was also an increase in the percentage urban population.

A total of 7.18% of Nigeria’s population lived in urban centres while 92.82% were rural inhabitants. The percentage rose to 19.30% and 36.30% respectively between 1963 and 1991 as indicated on table 1 below. The United Nation (2000) projected that by the end of 2050 half of the world’s population will live in urban centres.

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

Table 1: Number and growth of urban cities in Nigeria (Population 20,000 person)

Year	Population (in thousand)		Total population (in thousand)	No of Urban Cities	% of Urban Pop	% from 1921	
	Rural	Urban				Rural	Urban
1921	17.375	1,345	18,720	29	7.18		
1931	18,625	1,431	20,056	27	7.14	0.42	2.79
1953	27.166	3,237	30,403	56	10.65	1.42	2.76
1963	44.925	10,745	55,670	182	19.30	2.29	5.01
1991	57,185	31,807	88.992	359	36.3	1.70	4.52

Source: NPC, 1991 Population census

The increasing Nigeria urban centres and population is occurring without generating the needed resources and employment opportunities to accommodate the surge in population. The concentration of economic activities in urban centres creates disparity in the economic growth between urban and rural areas. The less privileged and poor migrants who move from rural areas to urban centres in search of employment, security and safety, find themselves living in slum settlements within and around urban centres. As more people moved into an urban center voluntarily or forced by administrative compulsion, many social maladies become noticeable in the city. This group of people who suffer extreme deprivation and exclusion later indulge into a wide range of criminal activities. Crime is an action or omission which constitute an offence and is punishable by law. In modern criminal law crime does not have any simple universally accepted definition. A crime or offence is an act lawfully not only to individuals but also to a community, society or the states (Wikipedia Encyclopedia, 2008). Criminologists have grouped crime into two major categories – felonies and misdemeanors. According to Paul Tappen, crime is an international act or omission in violation of criminal law committed without defence or justification and sanctional by state as a felony or misdemeanor.

This study seeks to appraise the internal security and safety situation in the ancient city of Calabar arising from rapid population and urbanization, the physical structure and planning of the metropolis.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

There has been immense increase in population and urban expansion over the years in Calabar Metropolis. The official national population census conducted during the colonial administration revealed that Calabar had a total of 46,705 people in 1953 and 100,628 people in 1963 with percentage growth rate of 1.09. The next and most recent official census reported a total of 329,000 in 1991 and 375,196 in 2006 respectively.

Urban population growth becomes a significant problem when its consequences impact negatively on the environmental resources and threats to human lives. Among the most serious problems confronting Calabar Metropolis and its inhabitants include lack of employment opportunities, increasing poverty, housing shortage and expansion of squatter settlements, growing insecurity and rising crime rates, uncoordinated urban development and increasing vulnerability to disaster which are the basic issues of mankind in the societies.

The ancient city of Calabar is experiencing high rate of insecurity resulting from the presence of less privilege (poor) who suffer extreme deprivation and exclusion. These poor migrants who migrated from rural areas to Calabar in search of security, safety and gainful employment are found living in slum settlements without basic facilities and services. Calabar Metropolis has witnessed a wide range of criminal activities over a decade such as kidnapping, armed robbery, rape, murder, burglary, auto theft, arson etc.

These criminal activities occur in different geographical locations and settings (neighbourhoods) such as Bay side, Anantigha, Watt Market, Ekpo Abasi, Akim Qua, Big Qua, Ikot Ansa etc. Other locations that cluster criminal activities are entertainment clubs, super markets, stores, major motor parks and residential neighbourhoods, example the State, Federal and Private Housing Estates inhabited by relatively well-to-do, young and adults, abandoned and uncompleted public and private property etc.

III. AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to appraise the security and safety situation in Calabar Metropolis with a view to finding solution to the problem.

Objectives

1. To identify the major types of criminal activities in Calabar Metropolis
2. To determine the causes of such criminal activities in the study area
3. To examine the physical form and structure of the study area

Figure 3: Map of Calabar showing the Study Area
Source: Cross River GIA

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

The whole world including Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) are experiencing high rare of population growth and urban expansion. The United Nation (2008) reported that only 20 million people were living in urban areas in Sub-Saharan Africa. Todaro (2000) observed that the SSA region recorded the highest urban growth rate in the world with an average of 5% per annum. Hove, Ngwerume and Muchemwa (2013) reported a total urban population of 250 million. Accordingly, the United Nation Population Fund*UNPF (2000) concluded that at this rate of growth, urban population will double between 2000 and 2030 resulting to serve social, economic, physical and environmental consequences.

The poor migrant population in urban centres will create informal settlements with extreme human insecurity resulting to high rate of criminal offences ranging from major crimes referred to as felonies or predatory crimes and minor crimes otherwise known as misdemeanors. According to Obeng-Odoom (2011) these poor migrants constitute part of the urban poor who suffer extreme deprivation and exclusion. Rakisits (2008) also observed the growing number of street children like the Amajeris or Skolombos in the Northern and Southern States in Nigeria and destitute in our urban areas who survive through begging, stealing, casual work or crime as major consequences of deprivation. ‘Crime’ does not have a universally accepted definition. It has different meaning by different schools of thought. Paul Tappen, a criminologist, defined crime as an international act or omission in violation of criminal law submitted without defence or justification and sanctioned by state as a felony or misdemeanor. Felonies are major or serious crimes that attract death sentence or incarceration in a prison for several years by government. These include kidnapping, murder, rape, arm robbery, burglary etc. Misdemeanor or minor crimes are unserious crimes such as shoplifting, petty theft, pick pocking, simple assault etc which attract conferment in a local jail for at least a year.

Table 2: Major Crime Incidence in the Urban Areas and Rates per 100,000 Populations.

S/NO	CRIME	INCIDENCE	CRIME INDEX
I	Murder	19,645	7.4
ii	Forcible Rape	957,679	36.1
iii	Robbery	537,050	202.1
Iv	Aggravated Assault	1,029,814	388
V	Burglary	2,501,524	943
Vi	Larceny	7,894,620	2,925.9
Vii	Auto Theft	1,395,192	525.9
Viii	Arson	88,887	44.3
Total		13,562,501	5,078.9

Source: FBI (UCR), 1996

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

A summary of crime statistics compiled by the research department of Clean Foundation in collaboration with the Nigerian Police recorded about 26 criminal offences between 1994 and 2003 as shown on table 3 below.

Table 3: Crime Statistics in Nigeria (1994-2003)

OFFENCES	RECORDED INCIDENCE
Armed Robbery	25,352
Assault	377,568
Child Stealing	1,320
False Pretence	110,913
Forgery of Currency Note	6,759
Murder	17,448
Attempted Murder	2,434
Theft, Larceny and others	505,075
Burglary	64,863
Demand/Menace	1,824
Man Slaughter	259
Suicide	2,305
Attempted Suicide	754
General Hamm and Wounding	156,328
Coining Offence	211
Gambling	3,330
Rape	22,151
Slave Dealing	196
Breach of Public Peace	72,009
Perjury	903
House Breaking	72,574
Store Breaking	39,724
Bribery and Corruption	1,690
Escape from Lawful Custody	4,699
Kidnapping	3,589
Unnatural Offences	4,366
Total	1,488,644

Source: Clean Foundation, 2003

Global trends have shown a tremendous increase in crime rates over the years. Reports have shown an increase in crime from 2,000 to 2,300 for every 1000 people between 1980-2000. This showed that 60 percent of urban residents in developing countries have been victims of crime, over a five-year period with victimization rate of 70 percent in parts of Latin America and the Caribbean and Africa. According to the UN-Habitat, (2007) cities in Africa have the highest reported cases of burglary, with victimization rates of over 8 percent of the population. In the year 2000, the police in South Africa recorded 460 robberies for every 100,000 people. In Johannesburg for instance, 30 percent of residents were reported to have been victims of robbery.

Studies in urban and regional planning have continuously placed safety and security concerns within spatial context by examining design and policy intervention that can create defensible space (Newman, 1972; Frank and Engelke, 2001; Handy, Boarnet, Ewing and Killingswarth 2002). Environmental criminologists have placed much emphasize on the importance of geographical locations and architectural designs as factors that influence crime and its prevalence. It has been urged that certain urban design patterns such as neighbourhood design, street layout, avenues, alleys, boulevards, private homes and business establishments attract criminals and remain "Hotspots" and sites of high crime and deviate rates. Stark (1987) addresses such neighbourhood or communities as deviant neighbourhood which are characterized by dense population, with poor and overcrowded conditions that increase the temptation and opportunity to involve in crime and deviant behavior.

The built environment (neighbourhood) also present environmental constraints and opportunities which may be characterized by physical disorder (litter) and social disorder (crime). According to Ross et al (2001); Klinenberg (2002) living in a neighbourhood with such high physical and social disorder generates stress and fear. On the contrary, clean and safe neighbourhood attract outdoor activities. Recent studies have tried to ascertain the promotion of a safety and healthy community through the manipulation of urban design, land use and transportation. (Greenwald and Boarnet, 2002); Safety and security have been seen as

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

the most important environmental variables. Security has been defined by the Oxford Learner’s Dictionary as “the state of being free from danger or threat” and is one of the basic human needs. Human security protects communities and their inhabitants from insecurity and violence. Safety on the other hand refers to the environmental factors whose absence may lead to occurrence of crime and gives rise to threat and risk (Kelly and Dian 2009). It is interesting to note that the UN-Habitat (2007) have placed urban safety and security within the wider perspective of human security in our societies. According to Ogboi (2013) the level of safety differ among urban neighbourhoods especially the inner city and the suburban context.

VI. RESEARCH METHOD

The research study made use of the primary and secondary data. The official national population census data was obtained from the National Population Commission while the last official national census of 2006 was projected to 2020 at 3.0% growth rate. Data on crime was obtained from the Cross River State Criminal Intelligence Bureau (SCIB) Headquarters Calabar. Oral personal interview and direct observation were adopted to indentify crime hotspots and most especially the physical form of the city and its social and economic activity pattern, the structure of the city’s street network and neighborhood design.

The Pearson’s Product Moment (PPM) statistical instrument was employed to explore the relationship between population and crime variables as shown on tables 4 and 5 below.

VII. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

PRESENTATION OF RESULT

The results of the data were presented using simple percentages and bar charts as shown below

Table 4: Trend of population for Calabar metropolis based on official population census

S/n	Year	Population	Percentage (%)
1	1953	46,705	5.45
2	1963	100,628	11.82
3	1991	329,000	38.64
4	2006	375,196	44.06
	TOTAL	851,529	100.00

The results in Table 3 shows the trends in population for Calabar metropolis based on official population census revealed a total population of 851,529. While year 2006 had the highest population of 375,196 (44.06%), followed by 1991 with a population of 329,000 (38.64%), while the least was 1953 which has a population of 46,705 (5.45%).. This indicates that there is a geometric increase in the population of the respondents in Calabar metropolis. The result is also presented in a bar chart as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Bar chart of trends in population for Calabar metropolis based on official population census

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

Table 5: Estimated population figure for Calabar Metropolis

S/n	Year	Estimated population	Number of crime committed
1	2006	375,196	326
2	2007	367,458	211
3	2008	374,363	291
4	2009	386,989	172
5	2010	375,882	152
6	2011	365,605	156
7	2012	379,553	204
8	2013	386,277	319
9	2014	398,045	325
10	2015	422,286	364
11	2016	448,003	305
12	2017	475,286	335
13	2018	505,231	337
14	2019	534,938	250
15	2020	567,515	500
Total		3,737,581	4247

It is evident from the result in table 5 of the estimated population figure for Calabar Metropolis that the total estimated population for the fifteen years (2006-2020) is 3, 737, 581 and the corresponding number of crime committed within these years amounted to 4,247. Year 2020 had the highest crime rate of 500; this was followed by year 2015 that has a crime rate of 364 cases. While the least was year 2010 with an estimated crime rate of 152 accordingly. This implies that there is an arithmetic increase in the rate of crime committed between 2006-2020. The result is further presented in the bar chart in figure 5

Figure 5: Estimated population figure for Calabar Metropolis

Table 6: Major crime statistics in Calabar metropolis (2006-2020)

S/n	Year	Kidnapping	Cultism	Rape	Burglar y	Murder	Arson	Armed robbery	Theft	Auto theft	Vandalism
1	2006	7	-	9	10	18	5	37	240	-	-
2	2007	5	-	7	6	7	3	15	168	-	-
3	2008	4	-	16	9	15	2	21	224	-	-
4	2009	8	-	11	4	15	5	25	103	1	-
5	2010	4	-	8	7	15	-	18	99	1	-

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

6	2011	6	-	5	4	22	2	31	86	-	-
7	2012	7	-	16	5	31	3	36	106	-	-
8	2013	9	-	12	10	24	-	63	201	-	-
9	2014	7	-	15	8	26	2	24	243	-	-
10	2015	4	-	11	6	12	2	14	315	-	-
11	2016	9	-	15	16	5	3	45	199	-	-
12	2017	15	-	12	9	19	5	52	220	2	1
13	2018	6	6	11	5	22	1	38	238	5	1
14	2019	7	-	4	6	24	4	30	172	3	-
15	2020	8	4	35	10	26	10	41	342	4	16
Tot		106	10	187	115	281	47	490	2956	16	18
al											

It can be discerned from the statistical analysis in Table 6 of the major crime statistics in Calabar metropolis (2006-2020), theft has the highest with a total of 2956, this was followed by armed robbery 490 while those with murder cases came third with a total of 291 while the least are those who constitute the categories of cultism with a total of 10. The results are presented in the bar chart in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Bar chart of major crime statistics in Calabar metropolis (2006-2020)

VIII. TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant relationship between population and crime in Calabar metropolis.

The variables involved in this hypothesis are population and crime. To test this hypothesis, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Statistics was employed. The choice of this statistical tool was because the scored were measured and the researcher intends to explore relationship between the variables under study. The result is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Relationship between population and crime rate in Calabar metropolis (N=4247)

Variables	$\sum x$	$\sum y$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	df	LS	r-cal	p-value
Population (x)	63356		1017090						
Crime rate (y)		66664		2554366	513905720	4245	0.05	.78	.000

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

The result obtained in Table 7 revealed that with 4247 respondents as the estimated population figure for Calabar Metropolis. While X scores has a sum of 63356 sum of all scores squared of 1017090 while crime rate (y) scores has a sum of 66664 and sum of all scores squared of 2554366. The sum of product of x and y scores is 513905720 accordingly. At 4,345 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the p-value was found to be .000 which is less than the chosen alpha of .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between population rate and crime rate in Calabar metropolis. Aptly put, the greater the population the higher the rate of crime in Calabar metropolis.

Calabar Metropolis comprises of Calabar Municipality and Calabar South. The study revealed that the inner city neighborhoods are the crime Hotspots and further identified other crime endemic areas in the metropolis as shown on fig. 7.

FIG 7. CRIME HOTSPOTS IN THE CALABAR METROPOLIS

Source: Field Survey (2020)

Inner City Neighborhoods

- - - Local Govt. Boundary

• Surrounding Settlements

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

The geographic locations, architectural and urban design patterns, such as neighborhood design, street layouts, avenue, alley ways, boulevards, private homes and business establishments like the popular Watt market, Eka Ika Qua and Mbukpa market among others in the Calabar metropolis are the primary factors that influence crime and its prevalence. Other locations are Jonathan Bye-pass, Parliamentary extension, Akai Effa, Ikot Ishie, Ikot Ansa, etc in Calabar Municipality and Anatigha, Ekpo Abasi, Mbukpa, Edibe-Edibe etc in Calabar South.

Table 6 above shows constant increase in crime except for auto theft, vandalism and cultism from 2012-2014 which is the last quarter of the previous administration and from 2015-2020 towards the end of the present administration. Criminal activities dropped significantly during CONVID-19 pandemic which held criminal elements hostage (indoors) for fear of the deathly virus which is on-going in both developed and developing nations of the world. The year 2020 also witnessed serious civilian protest against the Nigerian Police Force tagged ENDSARS along the streets of Nigerian urban centres and Calabar in particular. This protest led to insecurity and safety of life and property in the Calabar metropolis. The period recorded an increase in theft, arm robbery, rape, murder, vandalism, burglary, arson, kidnapping, auto-theft and cultism respectively as shown on table 6 above. Within the period under study several public and private offices, business and commercial buildings were set ablaze, theft, arm robbery, rape, murder and vandalism were at their peak.

Below are places destroyed and looted within Calabar Metropolis during the ENDSARS protest - the Calabar International Conference Centre, the Newspaper Cooperation (Chronicle), the Cross River State Ministry of Works at Ekorinim which comprises the Vehicle Inspection Office (VIO), Government Warehouse, Training School, Mechanical Workshops, Cross River Independent Electoral Commission (INEC), West African Examination Council Office, Governor's Petrol Station, Garment Factory, Roll Back Malaria Office, Senators Houses, Access Bank, First Bank, National Television Authority (NTA) Value Mart Supermarket, University of Calabar Microfinance Bank etc.

Plate 1: Vandalized Calabar International Conference Centre

Plate 2: Vandalized Newspaper Cooperation (Chronicle) and Burnt Govt. Vehicles Barracks Road Calabar

Plate 3: State Ministry of Works Building at Ekorinim

Plate 4: Vandalized Vehicle Inspection Office (VIO) at Ekorinim

Plate 5: Burglarized Government Warehouse at Ekorinim

Plate 6: Vandalized Training School Ministry of Work at Ekorinim

Plate 7: Vandalized INEC Office, Marian Road

Plate 8: Vandalized Value Mart Super Market, Marian Road

Plate 9: Vandalized State Electrification Agency, Ministry of Works, Ekorinim

Plate 10: Rural Access Mobilization (RAM) Ministry of Works, Ekorinim

The study revealed that residents in the crime endemic neighbourhoods (Inner city) of the metropolis are impoverished in terms of resources availability with fewer opportunities to bridge the gap between the rich and the poor hence the tendency to indulge in criminal activities.

Among these crime endemic neighborhoods are Duke Town, Henshaw Town, Esuk, Watt Market, Etim Edem in Calabar South and Akim Qua, Big Qua Town, Diamond Town, Essien Town, Edeba, Ika-Ika Qua Market in Calabar Municipality. The deteriorating conditions and quality of life in these neighborhoods makes them criminogenic. The study further revealed that violent crime and delinquency rates are more prevalent among the lower socio-economic groups living in these neighborhoods and other crime locations.

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

Oral interview with the Nigerian Police Force in Calabar revealed Youth involvement in crime from the age of 12-21 and above which according to them is a reflection of the degree of social disorganization and deteriorating quality of urban life. According to the police force these crime endemic locations have the highest population of youth gangs who have masterminded the kidnapping of high profile government officials and business mogul for ransom to get rich quick.

The study further revealed high incidence of crime in the Gated and rich neighborhoods such as the Satellite Town, Ekorinim, State Housing Estate, Federal Housing Estate, House of Assembly village and other private housing estates within the metropolis. These rich neighborhoods are characterized with high wall fences which negates the Eye-on-the-street theory by Ross (2000) and Eyler and Vest (2002), Narrow and winding lonely streets with Dead-ends, and graffitis on fences and buildings such as “Beware of dogs”, car parked at owners risk” etc which attract criminality as shown on the plates below.

Plate 11: High wall fences and narrow Winding Street At Ekorinim Community (Crime Hotspot)

Plate 12: High wall fences at Satellite Town (poor Eyes-on-street)

Plate 13: Watt Market along Calabar Road (Crime Hotspot)

Plate 14: Beware of Dogs (Graffiti)

Plate 15: Cars Parked At Owner's Risk (Graffiti)

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

IX. CAUSES OF CRIME IN CALABAR METROPOLIS

Oral interview of selected groups of residents in the inner city neighborhoods and other crime locations and hotspots in the metropolis revealed the following factors as being responsible for crime in the study area.

Extravagant and flamboyant lifestyles; Driving and walking alone on dark streets; Building of high wall fences in rich residential neighborhoods; Poverty and deprivation; Leaving with house doors open; Leaving car keys in the ignition; Exposing valuable properties in the car; Indecent dressing code by women; Disintegration of urban and suburban areas through urban planning and architectural design; Poor policing of crime hotspots and lack of patrol vehicles; Unemployment; Rapid population and urbanization; Drug usage; The structure of political power and corruption; Religion and intergenerational transmission of violence; Family conditions; Lack of access to legitimate opportunities for minority groups; Deteriorating condition of urban neighborhoods and quality of life; Neighborhood streets with poor linear visibility and dead-ends; Incessant use of artifacts which include graffiti on city buildings and walls such as “Beware of dogs”, cars parked at owner’s risk etc are criminogenic; Poor funding of security personnel; Lack of security gadgets such as CCTV cameras; Poor urban planning, design and management.

X. CONSEQUENCES OF CRIME ON RESIDENTS OF CALABAR METROPOLIS

- There has been serious problem of insecurity and safety due to high rate of criminal activities in the Calabar Metropolis.
- Many business have folded up and businessmen have loss their savings to armed robbers and fraudsters in recent times.
- Rape victims for instance have suffered humiliation, embarrassment shame and serious depression. The psychological and physical trauma will live with the residents for a long time.
- Millions of Naira, personal properties and many lives have been lost especially during the ENSARS protest in Calabar. Insurance claims and premium are now high and many victims of vandalization may not be able to cope. Most victims and property owners suffered physical assault and majority are permently disabled due to high medical cost.
- Under the present economic down turn government may find it difficult to maintain the cost of security systems and many other crime prevention measures and apparatus. There is general fear in the system especially the frequent cases of kidnapping and assassination of high profile politicians and businessmen within the metropolis and its environ.

XI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Crime can be reduced through the encouragement of neighborhood watch and frequent policing of target areas of crime hotspots in Calabar Metropolis. Government should have democratized urban design and planning to accommodate all social groups) that is Integration between urban and suburban areas to reduce high crime rate. There should be stiffer penalties, faster court trails and sentences for crime victims. The public should be informed through public media to always take precautionary measures to safeguard their cars and home doors. The use of hard drugs by the youths should be closely monitored by the Nigerian Police Force. Brujak (1999) observed that the higher the proportion of young people especially the male counterpart in a city, the greater the incidence of violent crime. He further contended that the youth populations are more predisposed to crime than the elderly people. This shows that there is a relationship between age structure of population of a city and incidence of crime.

In its study, the FBI (1996) crime index shows that about 55.6 percent of offenders are between 18-25 years of age. Orphanage homes in the Calabar Metropolis should be a transformed as foundation for the welfare of youths and should be equipped to deal with the problem of child abandonment and street children popularly known as Skolombo in Calabar Metropolis, Amajiris and Damiskas in Northern Nigerian cities, Agberos and Alayes in Western parts of Nigeria and touts, street urchins and juveniles. The higher income class should be informed through public media to avoid extravagant and flamboyant lifestyles. Government and the organize private sector should introduce youth empowerment programme or employment opportunities for the poor youths in our societies to reduce inequality and denial justice which fosters and engenders criminal activities. There should be synergy among ethnic, religious and political groups to co-exist in harmony with one and another. Government curfew laws should be enforced to reduce crime in hot spots of the Calabar metropolis as shown on fig 7.

Urban and regional planners should develop safety base designs for urban spaces such as residential and commercial neighborhoods, parks and recreational grounds, street networks and urban renewed projects.

The “Eye on the street” defined by Jacobs (1961) as a natural surveillance that is a deterrent of criminal activities should be adopted in street network design. It is seen as the resident ability to view public streets. The design orientation of buildings with windows directly facing the street increases natural surveillance for residents of rich neighborhoods such as Ekorinim, Satellite Town, Public and private residential estates in Calabar Metropolis. High wall fences and heavy landscaping should be discouraged in rich neighborhoods as they block view and create hideouts for criminal activities like rape and handbag snatching. Street lighting along major and minor streets should be encouraged as well as public open spaces and parking lots to scare criminals and hoodlums. Undeveloped plots of land should be cleared and maintained while uncompleted buildings and open parks should be policed more frequently by law enforcement officers. The Cross River State Government should key into the crime prevention technology in major urban areas in the state through the use of video surveillance (Close Circuit Television Camera (CCTV) to monitor criminal

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

activities in the cities. Other crime prevention technology such as electric fencing, security breach alarm systems, auto-breach sensor and so on, should be utilized to reduce auto-theft, license plate recognition technology, and the use of Geographic positioning systems (GPS) should also be used to monitor criminal activities in our urban areas.

XII. CONCLUSION

Urbanization is a product of rapid population growth of an area. It is an important component for the economic and social development of an area with its attendant consequences such as unemployment, poverty, crime, insecurity and safety. Calabar Metropolis has witnessed a wide range of criminal activities, at different geographical locations by both physical and social disorder. Other factors that influenced crime and its prevalence in Calabar Metropolis include architectural and urban design pattern such as neighborhood design, the structure of the city's street layouts, private homes, offices business establishments etc.

It must be noted that security and safety are the major objectives of physical planning to reduce crime rate in our urban centres. Urban planners should develop appropriate designs and opportunities to minimize the rate of criminal activities in the urban centres. Government in partnership with the private sector should employ appropriate security apparatus, skill security personnel, modern technology and other measures to promote the security and safety of residents in the study area.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge the Authors whose materials and publications guided us in this research as indicated in the Bibliography section. We also want to thank our wives and children who allowed us to be away from them at the course of this research and the cab man who took us round the city of Calabar in order to get important information and photographs needed for this study. Above all, we give God the Glory for wisdom, understanding and knowledge bestowed on us to complete this work.

REFERENCES

- 1) Brantingham, P. (2005) "Daily Urban Crime and Disorder: Is there a simple solution? Canada. Institute for Urban Research Studies. Simon Frazer University.
- 2) Bryjak, G. J. (1999) "Multiple Reasons for Lower Crime Rates" San Diego Union Tribune. March 28.
- 3) Federal Bureau of Investigation (1996) "Uniform Crime Report" Washington D.C. Government Office.
- 4) Federal Bureau of Investigation (1996) Crime in the United States" Washington D.C. Government office.
- 5) Frank L. D. and Engelke P. O. (2001) "The Built Environment and Human Activity Patterns: Exploring the Impacts of Urban Form and Public Health". Journal of Planning Literature. Vol.16 No.2 Pp. 202-218.
- 6) Greenwald M. and Boarnet M. G. (2002). The Built Environment as a Determination of Walking Behaviour: Analyzing Non-work Pedestrian Travel in Portland, Oregon", Transportation research record. Journal of Transportation Research Board, No. 1780, TRB, National Research Council, Pp. 32-42.
- 7) Handy S. (1996) "Urban Form and Pedestrian Choices Study of Austin Neighborhood". Transportation Research Record 1522, TRB. National Research Council.
- 8) Handy S. L., Boarnet M. Ewing R. and Killingworth R. E. (2002) "How the Built Environment affects Physical Activity; views from Urban Planning". American Journal of Preventive Medicine, Vol. 23. Nov. 2 (Supplement), Pp. 64-73.
- 9) Hicks, J. (1998) "Enhancing the Productivity of Urban Africa" Being paper Published in the Proceedings of an International Conference Research Community for the Habitat Agenda: Linking Research and Policy for the Sustainability of Human Settlement held in Geneva, July 6-8. 1998.
- 10) Hove, M., Ngwerume E. T. and Muchemwa C. (2013) "The Urban crisis in Sub-Saharan Africa: A threat to Human Security and Sustainable Development". Stability: International Journal of Security and Development 2(1).
- 11) Jacobs, J. (1961) "The Death and Life of Great American cities, Vintage Books, New York.
- 12) Kelly E. & Dian D. C. (2009) Securing the Built Environment: An Analysis of Crime Prevention through Environmental Design Ball University, Munie Indiana.
- 13) Kelingberg, E. (2002) Heat Wave: A social autopsy of disorder in Chicago. The University of Chicago Press.
- 14) Newman, O. (1972) Dejenisible space: Crime Prevention through Urban Design. New York. Macmillan.
- 15) Nnodu V. C, Okoye, Onwuka (2008) Urban Environmental problems in Nigeria. Rex Charles and Patrick Limited, Booksmith House, Harmony Place, Nimo, Anambra State, Nigeria.
- 16) NPC (1998), 1991 Population Census of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Nigeria Population Commission, Abuja.
- 17) Obeng-odoom, F. (1981) :Informal sector in Ghana under Siege" Journal of Developing Societies, Vol. 27 no. 3-4 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0169796x1102700406>.
- 18) Ogboi, K. C. (2013) "Enhancing Urban Security and safety in Nigeria through Parks, S. E. Honsemann R. A. and Brownson R. C. (2002) Differential Correlates of Physical Activity in Urban and Rural Adults of various socioeconomic Background in the U.S. Journal of Epidemiolog and Community Health. Vol. 57, Pp. 29-35.

An Appraisal of Insecurity and the Consequences on Residents in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria

- 19) Okeke, D. C. (2002) *Environmental and Urban Renewal Strategies: Theoretical and Analytical Frameworks*. Institute for Development Studies, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, Nigeria.
- 20) Rakisits, C. (2008) "Child soldiers in East of Democratic of Congo". *Refugee Survey Quarterly*, 27(4): 108-122. DOI:[http://dx.doi.org/10.1093 req/hdno54](http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/ref/hdno54).
- 21) Rose, C. E. (2000) "Walking Exercising, and smoking: Does neighborhood matter?" *Social Science and Medicine*. Vol. 51, No. 2, Pp.265-274.
- 22) Stark, R. (1987) "Deviant Places: A theory of the Ecology of Crime" *Criminology* Vol. 25, No. 4.
- 23) Todaro, M. (2000) *Economic Development*, Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
- 24) United Nations, (1996) *An Urbanizing World: Global Report on Human Settlements 1996*. A United Nation Publication. New York.
- 25) UN-Habitat (2008) *State of the World's Cities Report*, Nairobi, Kenya: UN-Habitat United Nations Population Fund (2007), *State of World Population 2007: Unleashing the potential of urban growth*, accessed online at www.un7pa, on 3 Jan. 2013. United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA) (2011) *Population Distribution, Urbanization, Internal Migration and Development: An International Perspective*. New York City, NY.